

Job Satisfaction of Employees in Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited (BHEL), Tiruchirappalli

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ABSTRACT

The Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited is one of the major industries for country's economic development. The main aim of this study is to assess the factors which are responsible for employee's job satisfaction. This paper aims to study relationships in among reasonable compensation and job satisfaction, working environment and job satisfaction, Job Security and job satisfaction. The result exposed that salary is the mainly important factor for influence job satisfaction of employees. Apart from salary, it has been found that the influence of supervisor support, healthy working environment, proper work-life balance, career opportunities and promotion, proper training and development opportunities are furthermore very important factors for determining employee's job satisfaction. Data is collected using questionnaires from 50 Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited employees who are randomly selected from the BHEL, Tiruchirappalli. Simple random sampling method was used in the study to select the sample. Reliability test, Principal Component Analysis, Independent Samples t-test, ANOVA and Mean Comparison test were used for analyzing the data.

Keywords: *Employees, Job satisfaction, ANOVA, Reliability test, Principal component analysis*

INTRODUCTION

Organizations today are facing major challenges in terms of competition, innovation, productivity and work force diversity. In this context, Employee Job

Satisfaction can be seen as a revelation of employee's preferences over jobs. Job satisfaction or employee satisfaction is the level of workers feeling regarding his or her job. This sentiment is mainly based on an individual's opinion of satisfaction. Job satisfaction can be influenced by a person's ability to complete required tasks, the level of communication in an organization, and the way management treats employees.

This study is the application of this Job satisfaction concept on employees working Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited (BHEL), Tiruchirappalli and assessment of their satisfaction level towards their jobs. The study mainly aims to analyze perceptions of employees of BHEL on their rendering jobs and satisfaction level of those employees on their rewards, promotions, organizational environment.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ronan (1970) has studied the relative importance of eighteen job characteristics in relation to job satisfaction and found that job security is not important o salaried workers but it is important o both managerial and hourly workers.

Shrivastava and Purang (2009) conducted a study to examine the level of job satisfaction among employees of public and private banks in India. Results indicated that the means of the public and

private banks were significantly different from each other. It was found that private sector bank employees perceive greater satisfaction with pay, social, and growth aspects of job as compared to public sector bank employees. On the other hand, public sector bank employees have expressed greater satisfaction with job security as compared to private sector bank employees. These findings revealed that private bank employees received high pay, had more chances of promotion so they showed high job satisfaction.

Nimalathan (2010) conducted a study to examine the relationship between employees' level job satisfaction and performance among employees of People's Bank in Jaffna Peninsula, Sri Lanka. The results of the study revealed that, there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and employees' work performance. That is high level of fair promotion, reasonable pay system, appropriate work itself and good working condition leads to high level of employees' performance.

Grover and Wahee (2013) conducted a study on factors influencing job satisfaction of employees in Delhi/NCR. The result indicated that 7 factors viz. fairness, working conditions, job security, performance, salary and other benefits, comfortable working environment, training and demographic factors (gender, age, income, years of experience, and occupation of an employee) have significant influence on Job satisfaction. This study found that working environment seems to be one of the most important ingredients of job satisfaction followed by job security, salary and benefits and training. Secure job environment enhances the degree of job satisfaction.

Boundless (2016) defined job satisfaction as Job satisfaction can be influenced by a person's ability to complete required tasks, the level of communication in an organization, and the way management treats employees. Job satisfaction falls into two levels: effective job satisfaction and cognitive job satisfaction. Effective job satisfaction is a person's emotional feeling about the job as a whole. Cognitive job satisfaction is how satisfied employees feel concerning some aspect of their job, such as pay, hours, or benefits.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To analyses the job satisfaction of employees working in BHEL, Tiruchirappalli

To understand the perception of employees towards their jobs working in BHEL, Tiruchirappalli

Hypotheses

H01-There is no significant difference between Gender group of employees and their job satisfaction.

H02-There is no significant difference among experience of employees and their job satisfaction

H03-There is no significant difference among Salary of employees and their job satisfaction

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is an empirical study based on Primary data collected from employees working in BHEL based on their job satisfaction. Empirical studies are the collection and analysis of primary data based on direct observation or experiences in the 'field'. For collecting primary data, direct interview method has been used. For this purpose schedule (Structured questionnaire) has been used.

The data type in this questionnaire comprises nominal data (qualitative) and measurement data (Quantitative). As measurement scaling techniques, continuous scale (Likert five point) have been used. All Questions are close ended questions. Questionnaire includes three levels which are Demographic profile and statements related to job Satisfaction. Job satisfaction has been assessed by using Likert five point scale. The study has been surveyed a cross section of employees in a day.

Limitations of the Study

The study was conducted based on only thirty employees from BHEL.

The duration of study is only two months.

The data has been collected while employees were working. So there is a chance of biased information.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Reliability and validity of Questionnaire

Reliability is checked with Cronbach's Alpha. Alpha is 0.717 (Acceptance level-71%)

Validity is tested through consultation with the experts. Scott Smith (2013) also has been used for preparing questions.

RELIABILITY

Reliability Statistics			
Cronbach's Alpha		N of Items	
.717		13	
Final	Questionnaires	Mean	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
1	Are you enjoying the job	4.03	.738
2	Are you feel a sense of pride in doing your job.	4.30	.734
3	Are you like your supervisor	3.70	.720
4	Are you like the people working with your organization	3.67	.716
5	Communications seem good within this organization.	4.72	.732
6	Are you feel that the organization paid a fair amount for your work	3.53	.655
7	Are you getting with your timely promotion (Salary increment)?	4.23	.622
8	Are you satisfied with your timely promotion (Salary increment)?	4.13	.673
9	The rules and procedure of the organization makes you to doing good job	4.10	.667
10	When you do a good job, you receive the recognition from organization	3.97	.706
11	Are you satisfied with the benefits which you receive from organization?	4.40	.713
12	The benefits which you receive are as good as most other organizations offer.	4.85	.629
13	Are you receive all the benefits which you up to your knowledge?	4.43	.717

Demographical Profile

	Demographical Profile	n=50	
		Frequency	Percentage
Designation of Employees	Accounts Officer	2	4.0
	ADDL. Engineer	6	12.0
	ASSTT Engineer	9	18.0
	Chief Technician	10	20.0
	Master Technician	12	24.0
	Technician	11	22.0
Age	< 25	5	10.0
	26 to 35	18	36.0
	36 to 45	20	40.0
	> 45	7	14
Gender	F	48	96.0
	M	2	4.0
Salary	25000 - 35000	22	44.00
	35000 - 45000	9	18.0
	45000 -55000	12	24.0
	55000 - 65000	4	8.0
	> 65000	3	6.0

Dem	Ographical Profile	n=30	
		Frequency	Percentage
Education	Diploma	33	66.0
	BE	14	28.0
	UG	-	-
	PG	3	6.0
	Other	-	-
Marital Status	Married	38	76.0
	Unmarried	12	24.0
Experience	Up to 5 years	8	16.0
	Up to 10 years	15	30.0
	Up to 15 years	20	40.0
	Up to 20years	7	14.0

Test of Normality

Hypothesis Test 1- There is no significant difference between Gender group of employees and their job satisfaction (Independent Sample t-test)

	Gender	Group Statistics			
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Satisfaction	M	48	4.7500	.43759	.5000
	F	2	4.5000	.70711	.06316

To conduct an independent samples t test, we need one categorical or nominal independent variable and one continuous or interval scaled dependent variable (Urdan & Timothy.C, 2011).

With t-test, there will be one independent variable and one dependent variable. The independent variable can only have two levels (Male & Female) and the dependent variable should be measure data. As dependent variable (Job Satisfaction) all statements measured by likert five point scales have been considered

Independent Samples Test							
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means			
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference
Satisfaction	Equal variances assumed	.640	.428	-.779	48	.440	-.25000
	Equal variances not assumed			-.496	1.032	.705	-.25000

Here the significant Value is 0.44. i.e more than P-Value. So Accept the Null Hypothesis. Therefore, from table it can be interpreted that there is no significant difference between gender group of employees and their job satisfaction.

In order to make decision towards each hypothesis based on each products and services we consider two tailed significant value (P-value). For this purpose we consider significant value of Levene's Test for Equality of Variances. Where if significant value is less than Alpha value (.05) we go for next Pvalue (Sig 2-tailed) of equal variance assumed or Equal value of not assumed. If sig value of Levene's Test for Equality of Variances

more than Alpha value (.05) we consider p-value of 'equally variance assumed', unless we consider p-value of 'equally variance not assumed'.

Hypothesis Test-2- There is no significant difference among experience of employees and their job satisfaction

		Descriptive				
Job Satisfaction						
Year of Experience	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
5Yrs	8	4.1364	.32141	.22727	1.2486	7.0241
10Yrs	15	4.0000	.25713	.18182	1.6898	6.3102
15 Yrs	20	4.2000	.36590	.16364	3.7457	4.6543
20 Yrs	7	4.3000	.33209	.10502	4.0624	4.5376
Total	50	4.1661	.29465	.05471	2.0541	4.2782

In case, if independent variable has more than two levels/Groups with Continues data then we would use one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Here, In order to understand the perceptions of Employees on Job satisfaction, likert five point scale have been used.

Experience has four levels/groups (Independent Variable)

		ANOVA				
Job Satisfaction						
Year of Experience	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Between Groups	.417	1	.069	.758	.610	
Within Groups	2.014	48	.092			
Total	2.431	49				

In ANOVA table the results are given in three rows. The first row labeled between groups which show the variability between the groups and second row shows variability within the groups. The third row gives total variability among all groups. Here F-value is .758 and corresponding Significant Value is 0.610 . Since P-value is more than significant Alpha value (.05) or 95% Confidence Interval value (0.113 > .05) we accept null hypothesis. Therefore, we can safely accept null hypothesis (Ho) and conclude that there is no significant difference variation in the perception of customers towards Islamic micro finance across profession.

Hypothesis-3- There is no significant difference among Salary of employees and their job satisfaction

Sl.No	Level of Salary	Frequency	Percentage
1	25000 - 35000	22	44.00
2	35000 - 45000	9	18.0
3	45000 -55000	12	24.0
4	55000 - 65000	4	30.0
5	> 65000	3	6.0

		ANOVA			
		Satisfaction			
Salary	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.443	1	.111	.200	.936
Within Groups	13.857	48	.554		
Total	14.300	49			

Post Hoc Test

		<i>Satisfaction</i>	
		<i>Duncan</i>	
<i>Salay</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Subset for alpha = 0.05</i>	
		<i>1</i>	
<i>25000 - 35000</i>	22	2.50	
<i>45000 - 55000</i>	12	2.50	
<i>35000 - 45000</i>	9	2.71	
<i>55000 - 65000</i>	4	2.75	
<i>> 10000</i>	3	3.00	
<i>Sig.</i>		.438	

The hypothesis test on salary group and Job satisfaction reveals that the significant Value is 0.936. This is greater than P-Value (.05). So accept the null Hypothesis

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The Hypothesis Test on Gender group of employees and their job satisfaction is reflecting that there is no significant difference between gender group of employees and their job satisfaction. Therefore, it can say that, the impact of gender wise job level is not effecting on their job satisfaction.

The Hypothesis Test on experience of employees and their job satisfaction explicit that there is no significant difference among experience of employees and their job satisfaction. Therefore, it can say that, the impact of experience of employees is not effecting on their job satisfaction.

The Hypothesis Test on Salary of employees and their job satisfaction indicates that there is no significant difference among Salary of employees and their job satisfaction. So that, it can be inferred from analysis

that, the impact of experience of employees is not effecting on their job satisfaction.

The highest mean value towards each statement recorded on “The benefits which you receive are as good as most other organizations offer” (Mean Value: 4.85) and “Communications seem good within this organization” (Mean value: 4.72). That means workers highly satisfied in these conditions of company.

CONCLUSION

The study is job satisfaction of employees working in BHEL, Tiruchirappalli illustrates that they have good perception on their job condition and working environment at this company. Though, many workers highly experienced in same company but most of them are salaried in between 25000-35000. All the

hypotheses test accepting null hypothesis i.e. there is no significant difference among gender, experience and salary and their job satisfaction. The study has been limited fifty employees and cross sectional data collection has been done within two months. Therefore, the real results and impacts of job satisfaction may not be resulted by this study. Though, based on this empirical study it can be concluded that, employees have good satisfaction on their jobs at BHEL, Tiruchirappali.

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